

AGRICULTURE MONITORING SYSTEM USING IoT

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ABSTRACT—The improvement of plantation methods and the rise in productivity both contributed to the expansion of the agriculture sector. The use of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies in agriculture has the greatest potential to increase productivity. Every year, the world's population rises. Therefore, the farming sector must employ cutting-edge technologies like IoT for improved profit in order to feed this large population. Reduce water waste and improved field monitoring are two benefits of Smart farming using IoT technologies. This paper introduces a system that monitors agriculture smartly using IoT. Farmers can use a smartphone application to monitor and manage the irrigation system in this suggested system from any location. The mobile application retrieves these values from the cloud and displays them to the user, allowing them to monitor the system using this application. The IoT system communicates the sensor values to reach the cloud. Through networked soil sensor, humidity and other Sensors capable of communicating with the farmers, this project provides improved irrigation and monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture stands as a cornerstone of human civilization, underpinning the very foundation of our survival and economic development. Human societies have thrived because agriculture has provided not only food but also raw materials for production since the first days of settled communities.. Compounding these challenges are the effects of climate change, which pose significant threats to agricultural productivity. Climate change can lead to unpredictable weather patterns, including more frequent and severe droughts, floods, and storms. These harsh weather events can devastate crops, reduce yields, and disrupt the stability of food supplies. Moreover,

rising temperatures can alter growing seasons and geographic suitability for certain crops, forcing farmers to habituate to new conditions or switch to various types of agriculture altogether. Water scarcity is another critical issue exacerbated by climate change. Agriculture is a major consumer of water, accounting for approximately 70% of global freshwater withdrawals. In many regions, water resources are already stressed, and the situation is hopeful to worsen with increasing demand and the impacts of climate change. Efficient water management is therefore essential To guarantee that agricultural needs are met without depleting this vital resource. Soil degradation is yet another significant concern. Intensive farming practices, deforestation, Poor land management has caused to the depletion of soil nutrients, erosion, and loss of soil organic matter. Healthy soils are important for sustaining agricultural productivity, as they support plant growth, retain water, and provide essential nutrients. Addressing soil degradation requires Sustainable land management practices that are long-term, can restore and maintain soil health.

The integration of advanced technologies such as IoT has become a promising response to these formidable challenges and solution to enhance agricultural productivity, sustainability, and resource management. Connected devices and sensors are used to improve agricultural productivity through IoT technology in agriculture, commonly referred to as 'Smart Farming' or 'Precision Agriculture'. The data-driven approach allows farmers to monitor parameters like soil moisture, humidity, temperature, and nutrient levels, which is beneficial. The agricultural sector can address

challenges faced by it through the use of IoT technology, which offers several key benefits. Precision farming is the primary reason for its implementation, which permits farmers to make the most of resources such as water, fertilizers, and pesticides. Farmers can decrease waste, lower costs, and minimize the environmental impact of their operations by utilizing these inputs only when they are needed. Using soil moisture sensors, water availability in the root zone can be monitored in real-time, allowing for precise irrigation scheduling and water availability.

In addition, this proactive approach has the potential to lead to healthier crops and higher yields. By constantly monitoring environmental conditions, IoT systems can give farmers the peace of mind of knowing about extreme weather events. Thirdly, IoT technology enhances decision-making capabilities by utilizing data analytics and predictive modelling. By examining both historical and real-time data, farmers can uncover insights into trends and patterns that influence crop growth and overall productivity.

This information can be utilized to predict future conditions, organize planting and harvesting timelines, and enhance farm management strategies. For instance, insights into soil nutrient levels can guide fertilization choices, ensuring that crops receive appropriate nutrients at optimal times. Beyond these advantages, IoT technology can improve traceability and transparency within the agricultural supply chain. By monitoring the environments in which crops are cultivated, harvested, and transported, IoT systems can offer comprehensive information to consumers and stakeholders regarding the origins and quality of agricultural products. This level of transparency can foster trust, enhance food safety, and promote sustainable and ethical farming practices. Nevertheless, the integration of IoT technology in agriculture presents certain challenges. A significant obstacle is the expense associated with implementing IoT systems, which may be unaffordable for small-scale farmers. Furthermore, there is a requirement for technical knowledge to install, maintain, and analyse data from IoT devices. Connectivity issues may also arise in rural regions where internet access is sporadic or unreliable.

Despite these challenges, the potential benefits of IoT technology in agriculture are substantial. Governments, industry, and research institutions are increasingly recognizing the importance of IoT and are investing in initiatives to support its adoption. For example, policies and programs that provide financial incentives, technical training, and infrastructure development can help overcome the barriers to IoT implementation. In conclusion, agriculture remains a cornerstone of human civilization, providing the fundamental resources needed for survival and economic development. As the global population grows and the challenges of climate change, water scarcity, and soil degradation intensify, the agricultural sector must innovate to meet these demands. The integration of IoT technology offers a promising solution to enhance agricultural productivity, sustainability, and resource management. By enabling precision farming, improving environmental monitoring, and supporting better decision-making, IoT can help secure the future of agriculture and ensure that it continues to sustain human life. IoT in agriculture, often referred to as Smart Farming, involves the use of connected devices and sensors to gather critical data from the farming environment. These devices can monitor various parameters such as soil moisture, humidity, temperature, and nutrient levels. The collected data is then transmitted to a central system where it can be analysed and used to optimize farming practices. This technology enables precision agriculture, which enhances resource efficiency, improves crop yields, and promotes sustainable farming methods. This project focuses on designing and implementing an agriculture monitoring system that utilizes soil moisture and humidity sensors. The system employs an Arduino microcontroller for data collection and a Bluetooth module for wireless data transmission.

A mobile application developed using MIT App Inventor serves as the user interface, allowing farmers to access real-time data and make informed decisions regarding irrigation and crop management.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

India is among the top five producers globally, contributing to over 80% of agricultural output. The rising demand for food, driven by population growth and increased income levels, has led to agricultural

technologies that enhance global crop yields by as much as 67%. To address the challenges posed by climate change in agriculture and to boost sustainable production methods to nourish the planet, modern agriculture increasingly employs various technologies and electronic devices, including robots, temperature and moisture sensors, and aerial systems, images, and GPS technology. Because of advanced devices, precision systems, agriculture and robotic businesses become more profitable, efficient, safer, and more environmental friendly. Smart farming, leveraging IoT technologies, allows agricultural producers to minimize waste and improve productivity, affecting various factors such as fertilizer usage and the frequency of farm vehicle trips, while also facilitating the effective use of resources like water and electricity. IoT smart farming solutions comprise a system designed to monitor crop fields through sensors that track light, humidity, temperature, soil moisture, and crop health, in addition to automating irrigation processes. Farmers can oversee field conditions remotely and choose between manual and automated methods to respond to the data collected. For instance, if soil moisture levels drop, sensors can be activated to initiate irrigation. Compared to traditional methods, smart farming demonstrates significantly greater efficiency. The potential of IoT to revolutionize agriculture is substantial, encompassing numerous critical aspects.

Data gathered through smart agriculture sensors plays a crucial role in this method of farm management. Essential components include sensors, control systems, robotics, autonomous vehicles, automated hardware, variable rate technology, motion detectors, button cameras, and wearable devices. This information can be utilized to monitor the overall status of the business, as well as evaluate staff performance and equipment efficiency. The capability to predict production outcomes facilitates improved planning for product distribution. Agricultural drones, both ground-based and aerial, are increasingly employed in agriculture to enhance a variety of practices, including crop health assessment, irrigation, crop monitoring, crop spraying, planting, and soil and field analysis. Predictive analytics in smart farming is essential for crop forecasting, as it enables farmers to make informed decisions about future production strategies, storage solutions, marketing approaches, and risk management. To estimate crop yield, artificial neural networks analyse data gathered from sensors deployed across the farm. This data encompasses various

parameters, including soil composition, temperature, atmospheric pressure, rainfall, and humidity levels. Farmers can access precise soil information through either a dashboard interface or a tailored mobile application.

III. METHODOLOGY

The structure of the agricultural monitoring system is composed of three primary layers:

1. Sensing Layer: This layer includes soil moisture and humidity sensors strategically positioned within the field.
2. Data Transmission Layer: This layer features a microcontroller and a Wi-Fi module that facilitate the transmission of data to the cloud.
3. Application Layer: This layer consists of a mobile application developed with MIT App Inventor, which allows for data access and analysis.

IV. OBJECTIVES

1. Develop an IoT-Based Agriculture Monitoring System:

- Design and build a system that integrates soil moisture and humidity sensors with an Arduino microcontroller to gather real-time environmental data.

2. Enable Wireless Data Transmission:

- Utilize a Bluetooth module to facilitate seamless and efficient wireless communication between the Arduino and a mobile application, ensuring that data can be accessed remotely.

3. Create a User-Friendly Mobile Application:

- Develop an intuitive mobile app using MIT App Inventor that allows farmers to easily monitor real-time sensor data, receive alerts for critical conditions, and access historical data trends.

4. Optimize Resource Usage and Improve Crop Management:

- Leverage the collected data to enable precise irrigation scheduling, reduce water wastage, and optimize fertilizer use, ultimately enhancing crop health and yield.

5. Promote Sustainable Agricultural Practices:

- Implement technologies that support sustainable farming by minimizing environmental impact, conserving water resources, and reducing dependency on chemical inputs.

6. Enhance Decision-Making and Farm Management:

- Provide farmers with actionable insights through data analytics, enabling better planning and management of farming activities based on current and predicted environmental conditions.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Hardware Setup:

The first step is to set up the hardware components. This includes connecting the soil moisture and humidity sensors to the Arduino, and integrating the Bluetooth module for wireless communication. Proper connections and configurations are crucial for accurate data collection and transmission.

Connecting Sensors: Soil moisture and humidity sensors are connected to the microcontroller board. The sensors are powered through the microcontroller's power pins, and data pins are connected to the respective analog/digital pins of the microcontroller.

Microcontroller Configuration: The microcontroller (ESP – 32) is programmed to read data from the sensors at regular intervals and send the data to the cloud via the Wi-Fi module.

Arduino Programming:

The subsequent phase involves developing the Arduino code responsible for acquiring data from the sensors and transmitting it through Bluetooth. This

code will encompass functions for initializing the sensors, periodically reading their values, and relaying the data to the Bluetooth module. The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) will be utilized for composing and uploading the code to the Arduino board. This process entails writing and uploading the code to enable the Arduino to read sensor data and transmit it via Bluetooth.

Mobile App Development:

A mobile application will be created utilizing MIT App Inventor to establish a connection with the Arduino. This application will incorporate functionalities to connect to the Bluetooth module, gather sensor data, and present it in an accessible format for users. Additionally, the application will feature alerts and notifications for situations that necessitate prompt action, such as insufficient soil moisture levels. The development of this mobile application through MIT App Inventor aims to facilitate the reception and display of sensor data while also offering notifications for urgent conditions.

System Testing:

To help identify any issues and allow for necessary adjustments to improve system performance. Conducting field trials to ensure the system's functionality and reliability, and to demonstrate its effectiveness in improving agricultural practices

Once the hardware and software components are in place, the system will be tested in a real-world agricultural setting. This involves deploying the sensors in the field, ensuring the Arduino and Bluetooth module are functioning correctly, and verifying that the mobile application accurately displays sensor data.

VI. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

A. ESP32 MODULE

The ESP32 is a highly capable microcontroller that features built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth functionalities, rendering it an excellent option for Internet of Things (IoT) initiatives. Created by Espressif Systems, the ESP32 enjoys significant popularity in applications that demand dependable wireless connectivity, energy efficiency, and strong performance.

B. DHT11 SENSOR

The DHT11 sensor is a popular digital sensor for measuring temperature and humidity. Known for its affordability and ease of use, it's widely used in DIY electronics projects, environmental monitoring systems, and home automation.

C. SOIL MOISTURE SENSOR

The soil moisture sensor is designed to assess the water content present in the soil. It generally comprises two probes that are inserted into the ground. The sensor evaluates the electrical resistance between these probes, which fluctuates in accordance with the moisture level of the soil. This information is essential for establishing an effective irrigation schedule, thereby ensuring that plants obtain sufficient water while minimizing waste.

D. HUMIDITY SENSOR

The humidity sensor used in this project will measure the relative humidity of the air. It consists of a hygroscopic material that absorbs moisture from the air, causing a change in its electrical properties. This change is converted into an electrical signal that the Arduino can read. Monitoring humidity levels helps in managing plant health, particularly in preventing fungal diseases that thrive in high humidity conditions.

E. BLUETOOTH MODULE

The Bluetooth module, such as the HC-05 or HC-06, facilitates wireless communication between the Arduino and a mobile application. It functions using a serial communication protocol, which permits the Arduino to transmit data to the mobile device over short ranges. This wireless functionality provides convenience for farmers, enabling them to monitor sensor data without requiring physical connections.

VII. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

A. Arduino IDE

To write, compile, and upload code to the Arduino microcontroller. The Arduino IDE provides a user-friendly interface for programming and debugging the microcontroller.

B. MIT App Inventor

A web-based platform designed for the creation of mobile applications through a visual programming interface. MIT App Inventor streamlines the app development process, rendering it accessible to those with minimal or no programming background.

C. Bluetooth Serial Terminal App: A mobile application designed to facilitate communication between an Arduino device and a mobile device through Bluetooth technology. This application provides functionalities for testing and debugging the Bluetooth connection.

VIII. CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

Step-1:

Connecting all the components as per the required output desired. These components must be carefully placed at the correct numbers in the esp-32 board as per the code that is used to upload in the Arduino IDE software, this provides the accurate output as desired.

Step-2:

Now, a perfect code needs to be designed using the libraries provided in the Arduino IDE software and check for any errors in the software, if any errors are produced, it needs to be cleared first. Later, the code needs to be uploaded and the stimulation has to run which produces the desired outputs on the serial monitor of the Arduino IDE software. The desired values are the values of soil moisture sensor which provides the value of moisture content of soil and humidity sensor which provides both humidity content and temperature values.

Step-3:

The values displayed in the Serial monitor are simultaneously displayed on the screen of the user either a smartphone or a PC, he can himself assess the values as they go on being displayed on the screen one after the other.

MIT APP INVENTOR DESIGNING

Step-1:

By using the MIT App tools, we can display the serial monitor outputs on the screen of the user which will be helpful for him to monitor the field according to it. This part plays a crucial role in the entire project, as the connection between the board and the MIT App software is done by using a Bluetooth module that is further connected in the App's tools as per the requirement.

Step-2:

The required buttons and display on the user's screen is enhanced by using the features provided by the MIT App, where we can use drag and drop buttons to establish the required display of the app. We can even design the Home page of the app attractive and user-friendly to establish a smooth working of the whole Application developed.

Step-3:

The values displayed in the Serial monitor are simultaneously displayed on the screen of the user either a smartphone or a PC, he can himself assess the values as they go on being displayed on the screen one after the other.

IX.BENEFITS AND IMPACT

The proposed agriculture monitoring system offers numerous benefits:

- **Resource Efficiency:** By providing precise data on soil moisture and humidity, the system enables optimized water usage and reduces wastage.
- **Enhanced Crop Yields:** Timely and accurate information helps farmers make better

decisions, leading to healthier crops and higher yields.

- **Sustainability:** The system promotes sustainable farming practices by conserving water and reducing the need for chemical inputs.

Ease of Use: The mobile application provides a user-friendly interface, making advanced agricultural technology accessible to farmers without requiring extensive technical knowledge

X. RESULT

The agriculture monitoring system project marks a pivotal advancement in utilizing IoT technology to tackle the urgent issues confronting the agricultural industry. By combining soil moisture and humidity sensors with an Arduino microcontroller and a mobile application created through MIT App Inventor, this initiative delivers a holistic approach to the real-time observation and management of agricultural environmental conditions. Notably, the project has successfully established an IoT-driven agriculture monitoring system that can gather and relay essential data regarding soil moisture and humidity levels. This system equips farmers with critical insights into the vitality and status of their crops, allowing them to make well-informed choices regarding irrigation, fertilization, and pest management. Additionally, the incorporation of wireless communication technologies, such as Bluetooth, ensures smooth data transfer between the Arduino and the mobile application. Farmers benefit from wireless connectivity that allows them to remotely access real-time sensor data, enhancing their ability to monitor crops with increased flexibility and convenience.

XI. CONCLUSION

The agriculture monitoring system project utilizes IoT technology to tackle significant challenges within the agricultural sector. By combining soil moisture and humidity sensors with an Arduino microcontroller and a mobile application, it delivers real-time data to farmers, allowing them to optimize irrigation, fertilization, and pest management. The system's wireless communication capability facilitates remote monitoring, and the intuitive app ensures that advanced

technology is easily accessible. This initiative encourages sustainable farming practices, minimizes resource consumption, and contributes to environmental sustainability. Ultimately, the project seeks to improve agricultural productivity, promote sustainability, and enhance food security for future generations.

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APPENDIX

(A) *Arduino IDE:*

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>

SoftwareSerial Bluetooth(10, 11); // RX, TX (Use
digital pins for SoftwareSerial if using Hardware
Serial for Serial Monitor)

int soilMoisturePin = A0; int humiditySensorPin = 2;

void setup() { Serial.begin(9600);
  Bluetooth.begin(9600);

  pinMode(humiditySensorPin, INPUT);
}

void loop() { int soilMoistureValue =
analogRead(soilMoisturePin); int humidityValue =
digitalRead(humiditySensorPin);

// Send sensor data to Serial Monitor
Serial.print("Soil Moisture: ");
Serial.print(soilMoistureValue);
Serial.print("\tHumidity: ");
Serial.println(humidityValue);

// Send sensor data via Bluetooth
Bluetooth.print(soilMoistureValue);
Bluetooth.print(",");
Bluetooth.println(humidityValue); delay(2000);
```

(B) *Initialize variable and connect to Bluetooth*

```
when ListPicker1.BeforePicking do
```

```
call BluetoothClient1.ScanForDevices
set ListPicker1.Elements to
BluetoothClient1.AddressesAndNames
```

```
when ListPicker1.AfterPicking do
call BluetoothClient1.Connect address
ListPicker1.Selection
if BluetoothClient1.IsConnected then
call Notifier1.ShowMessageDialog "Connected to " &
ListPicker1.Selection "Connected" "OK" when
ButtonConnect.Click do
if BluetoothClient1.IsConnected then
call BluetoothClient1.Disconnect
set LabelStatus.Text to "Disconnected"
else
call ListPicker1.Open
```

(C) *Receive and Display Sensor Data:*

```
when BluetoothClient1.ReceiveText do
set receivedData to
BluetoothClient1.ReceiveText "\n"
if receivedData contains ","
then set dataList to split at first receivedData ","
set LabelSoilMoisture.Text to
"Soil Moisture: " & select list item list dataList index
1
set LabelHumidity.Text to "Humidity: " & select list
item list dataList index
```